

SOCIAL AFFECT THROUGH RELATIONSHIP PUNJAB ORIGIN AND NON-ORIGIN BETWEEN FAMILY RELATIONS AND ADJUSTMENT

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Abstract:

This study aims to examine the relationship and differences between family relations and adjustment in the community environment of native Punjab adolescents and mixed Punjab adolescents in Medan Municipality, North Sumatra, Indonesia. The theory used is Bachman's family relation and adjustment from Schneider. This research is a survey with a correlation method, the target is all teenagers from the original Punjab tribe and mixed youth from the Punjab tribe obtained by census. The target population is 170 teenagers, namely 104 native Punjab teenagers and 66 mixed ethnic Punjab teenagers. The results showed that there was a relationship between family relations and adjustment in social life within the ethnic community, both in native Punjab adolescents and mixed Punjab adolescents.

Keywords: Social impact; family relations; adjustment; Punjab teenagers

I. Introduction

The family is the first and most important environment for children to start socializing. From here the child knows love, learns various life values, habits and recognizes personal responsibility as a consequence of his behavior which will be useful for the further development of the child's life.

There are positive family relationships and actions built on the basis of conversation, conformity, dependency and distribution of powers derived from parents and children as in families (Thariq, 2018). The interaction of a child with his parents, as the person who is closest and meaningful to him, is one of the factors that contribute to the development of a child's personality. In accordance with Hurlock's opinion that if the home atmosphere seen in the relationship between parents and children is marked by affection, respect, cooperation and tolerance, then the child will develop a healthy self-concept (Hurlock, 1973).

The family communication model in forming pious children was built by four foundations, namely the intensity of family communication consisting of frequency and duration of communication, family communication patterns consisting of atmosphere, communication and flow of communication, communication methods that tended to be persuasive and coercive, methods planting of value values consisting of exemplary methods, habituation, discipline, enforcement of rules that must be obeyed by children (Hendra et.al, 2019)

Children are also part of the young generation, as one of the human resources, which is the potential and successor to the ideals of the nation's struggle, which has a strategic role and has

special characteristics and traits. In maintaining this potential, children need coaching and protection in order to ensure physical, mental, and social growth and development as a whole, in harmony, in harmony, and in balance (Rizal et al, 2019)

In adjusting a person is also colored by the stages of development of his age. The target of this research is adolescence which is one of the development periods of human life which in the process will run smoothly or not influenced by environmental factors and individual experiences.

With the existing facts, the authors see that there are symptoms that can cause problems in adjusting to social life in the community, in the Punjab teenagers from northern India who are in the Municipality of Medan, North Sumatra, Indonesia. This is because the relationships prevailing in the family as well as those expected by the tribe of people to follow the customs are down and down from their ancestors.

The parents of the original Punjab tribe still follow the procedures of life in accordance with the customs of the ancestors both in terms of looking at children and in the care procedures provided. The position of boys and girls is still distinguished in obtaining formal education, even if there is a highest level of only high school and very few graduated from college, and some still do not complete elementary school (not school).

In family life, for example choosing a mate, a daughter is still obedient to the determination of her parents or siblings. Besides that, most parents do not want to accept the marriage of their children with other tribes, they consider that their tribes are better than other tribes. Teenagers want parents who do not distinguish between men and women both in providing attention, affection for education and in determining the future.

The treatment that parents will give is accepted by adolescents and the results will be seen in the behavior of adolescents, such as running away from home, marrying other tribes, resisting, resisting by misunderstanding between parent and child. This for native Punjab youth and mixed Punjab youth is already a violation of customs.

This fact occurs in the original Punjab tribe which is still guided by the way of life. Also occurs in mixed Punjab tribes. However, the native Punjab consider the mixed Punjab to have violated customs so that they have difficulty adjusting to social life.

Based on this description, this study will discuss the relationship between relationships in the family with adaptation to social life in the tribal community in native Punjab adolescents and mixed Punjab adolescents.

II. Literature Review

2.1 Family Relations

The family is the main pillar of life, especially for young generation. The family is the first educator and guard leader to realize human resources. For that the total support of the family is able to give birth as if a miracle in their life. Such is the urgency of the function of the family as the smallest organization in the structure of society that contributes to the character and the

mental state. Thus a strong nation depends on building a good family so that the family can become a pillar of development. But the hope of a formidable family to shape the nation's character and mentality is not always directly proportional to the reality in today's society. This is in line with family pressure even more severe because of the growing economic demands, technological developments to the increasingly heavy social changes as well. As a result the function of families in the community declined in the face of the nation's problems. Slowly but surely the weakness of family function has an impact on family resilience in shaping the character and mental of the nation. These family classic problems mentioned above, such as economy, education, and low access to healthy boards are still facing many Indonesian families. Unfinished, the family is already faced with more complicated new challenges. The development of internet, consumerism, fading of appreciation, respect and caring to others until the problem of narcotics circulation, dishonesty, corruption and radicalism increasingly undermined the function of the family. Not to mention on the other hand, globalization, increasing individualism and increasingly weak social control make the burden faced greater. (Thariq, 2018)

According to Steward and Koch (1983) family relations are the attitude of parents in interacting with their children. This attitude includes the way parents provide rules, discipline, gifts and punishments, and how parents show their authority and how parents give attention, affection and response to children.

Supported by the opinion of Peter (1991) that family relationships are patterns of relationships created between parents and children at home. In accordance with this opinion, the family relation intended in this study is in Bachman's opinion, which is the perception of the individual (child) regarding his relationship with parents and the attitude of parents towards themselves in the family environment.

Chairman of Center for Child and Family Welfare Studies Padjadjaran University Bandung Nunung (Kompas: 2017) said, only with the strength of family resilience, the various problems that can be passed. Weak family role will only give birth to a generation of weak and troubled nation. Still in Compass, according to Nunung, whatever happened to the nation all started from the family. Although the family plays an important role in determining the civilization of the nation, until now the family's development is still marginalized. Data from compass 2017, Indonesia has more than 65 million families. The new family development program is focused on economic empowerment. Along with the government's economic empowerment program, parents or families need to gain an understanding of the importance of the role of interpersonal communication in the family.

The re-affirmation of the importance of interpersonal communication in the family is considered to anticipate the impact of internet exposure and communication technology slowly but surely has changed the pattern of family communication and eroded family resilience. Direct face-to-face communication as a feature of interpersonal communication allows each party to read facial expressions, body language, to allow for a comfortable caress or touch between parent and child will shape the reality of family togetherness. That atmosphere can in

turn affect warm and supportive family relationships and actions that are characterized by mutual respect and mutual care. (Thariq, 2018)

a. Parents' Attitudes Toward Children

For a child, the family is the initial environment and the most important for him is the influence on the child's adjustment. Every experience that suggests that he is loved or rejected by someone else, will make adjustments and behavior according to the views of others (Burns, 1979).

Bachman (1967) also emphasized the importance of family, especially parents, in the formation of children's adjustment. It is said that the differences between people in the adjustment they have are closely related to the attitudes of parents and their parenting patterns, especially the warmth of parents (father and mother) and ways of applying rules or discipline to children.

According to Bachman (1967) family relations in question can be determined by the level of parental acceptance (closeness of relationship with father and closeness of relationship with mother), permissive attitudes of parents and those related to punishment and democratic attitudes of parents.

- Parental acceptance levels
- Permissive attitudes of parents and those related to the administration of law
- Democratic attitudes of parents

b. Factors That Influence Family Relationships

According to Hoffman and Lippit (in Mussen, 1970) there are several factors that can affect family relationships, including the background and background of children. So it can be concluded that in family relationships that occur in social processes between parents and children always involve parents as caregivers and children as caregivers.

2.2 Self-Adjustment

Providing understanding about adjustment is not easy. Each expert has a different concept of conformity, so the notion of conformity will depend on the approach used based on the theory adopted. Musthafa Fahmy (1996) provides the limits of adjustment as follows: adjustment is a dynamic process that aims to change their behavior so that a more appropriate relationship between themselves and their environment occurs.

Vembriarto (1984) said that the concept of self-adjustment in social science is called adjustment, which means adjustment such as adaptation to the physical environment and social environment both within the school family and community.

The problem of adjustment is not a simple problem but a problem that concerns all aspects of individual personality (Fahmy, 1982). Adjustment includes two aspects, namely personal aspects and social aspects. Personal adjustment means an individual's satisfaction with his own function and avoiding undue pressures.

a. Criteria for Good Adjustment

Some criteria for adjustment that are classified as good are characterized by the abilities put forward by experts as follows:

According to Kardatinata (1983) good adjustment has the following signs: (1) Able to work hard and be serious and try to get good results. (2) able to work orderly and in an orderly manner according to existing regulations, (3) able to work independently and be able to make their own decisions, (4) able to work alone without harming themselves or others, (5) responding to changes in the environment is not so rigid, (6) working with tenacity and endurance and tireless, (7) able to get along and participate in the activities of others.

2.3. Punjab

Medan Municipality consists of 11 districts and 144 sins with 329,772 households with a population of 1,807,466 people with a population density of 6,821 people / km². The number of households there is a small portion inhabited by a Sikh from the northern Punjab region of India totaling 1000 people. According to the writings of the writer shows that among the Sikhs themselves are not planted a sense of brotherhood and togetherness based on religion or ethnicity even some Sikhs are only selfish so often caused by small problems can result in quarrels within their own tribe. It is therefore desirable that such things did not happen so that Sikh children could go to school with a sense of security and security.

Punjabis are very strongly bound to the system of norms and customs, religion and language, has its own culture and religion that brought since the days of their ancestors for generations that characterizes them and is ultimately a way of life. Though generally they have been integrated with the people in the city of Medan, with a background of diverse cultures, but they are still determined to maintain the prevailing culture within the community, as they use the language of Punjabi and eating traditional foods commonly eaten, religious teachings which requires wearing turbans and scarves, traditional clothing and customs, such as childbirth, marriage and death events, and Punjab tribal days, while their religion has not been recognized in Indonesia.

The Punjab ethnic minorities, with the above characteristics, often make them constrained to adapt to the social environment outside their ethnicity, due to this ethnic tendency to maintain these characteristics in accordance with the culture and religious teachings they believe in their community. For example, in schools should choose and follow religious lessons other than Sikh religion, cutting hair, leaving clothes they must wear daily, which is a prohibition in religious teachings, this will be a constraint of social adaptation. If they do not do so they will face obstacles to adjustment, whether in the community such as work, interpersonal with others, and in the educational environment, so many Punjab community found that violates the teachings of his religion.

2.3.1 Traditional customs of Sikhs in the Family Environment

In everyday life the Sikh family's relationship between parents and children still follows the customs as did their ancestors. The cultural pattern is revealed in giving attention, nurturing

and developing children, giving love and education and determining their future through marriage. This applies to the older generation as well as the younger generation, although among those who have intermarried with other Indonesian tribes. They also have actually been influenced by the environment in which they live. However, they did not abandon the habits of their tribes which had been received from their parents for generations.

This situation applies to Sikhs in the Medan Municipality, including the relationship between parents and children in caring for their children in accordance with the customs of their tribe. If the behavior and actions are not in accordance with these habits, they are considered to have violated the customs and norms of their families and tribes.

III. Research Methods

In this study the Punjab adolescents as antecedent variables, family relations as the independent variable (X) and self-adjustment as the dependent variable (Y). The population in this study were all native and mixed young Punjab tribes in the Municipality with characteristics: unmarried, male and female, aged 11-30 years, still in school or not in school and who are Sikhs. The target population in this study were 170 people with 104 native Punjab teenagers and 66 mixed ethnic Punjab teenagers.

IV. Discussion

1. Relationship Between Family Relationships With Adjustment

Based on statistical testing it turns out there is a relationship between family relations with adjustment in native Punjab adolescents, men and women as well as in mixed Punjab adolescents. If we look at the results that will be obtained, it shows a low and very low relationship. However, at least it gives a hint that there is still a relationship between family relations and adjustment in both the native Punjab teenagers and mixed Punjab tribes.

This fact can be predicted that to achieve a good level of adjustment regarding emotional stability, sociability and objective thinking of adolescents is less explained or less related to family relations: funding the level of acceptance of permissive parents and with fathers and mothers), punishment and democratic attitudes parents only, but there are other possible factors that need attention.

The family is the first and most important environment for children, it is proven that there really is an effect on adjustment. Supported by the opinion of Hurlock (1974) that the family is one of the determining factors in adjustment. The opinion of Schneiders (1964) also supports this matter, according to him that adjustment is influenced by several factors, namely: physical condition, development and maturity, psychological factors, environmental conditions and cultural factors.

In this study it was found that in mixed ethnic Punjab adolescents, male and female, greater family relations had a relationship with adaptation than mixed ethnic Punjab adolescents. As for the native Punjab adolescent, male and female, aspects of family relations that are related

to greater adjustment are parents' permissive attitudes, whereas mixed Punjab adolescents, male and female, aspects of family relations related to adjustment are democratic attitude of parents.

This fact shows that to achieve better adjustment in the native Punjab adolescent, male and female, is influenced by the permissive attitude of the parents and which is related to punishment. In accordance with the existing situation that in this family, parents are still too strict and strong and are closed by the customs prevailing in the tribal community that was passed down from their ancestors so that the attitude of parents in this case let the child or do not want to know with children, but parents curb them. This can be seen in the lack of interaction between parents and children, but parents really expect children to comply with the prevailing customs, thus the relationship between parents and children is still rigid.

Whereas in mixed Punjab families, male and female, to achieve better adjustment is influenced by the parents' democratic attitude. This is in accordance with the existing situation that in this family parents have been influenced by customs from outside, in other words this encourages children to participate in discussions in dealing with problems. This situation is seen in the relationship of parents and children who are open or close and want changes to the customs that apply.

As stated by Bachman (1967) that disciplines that are strictly enforced or closed and excessive can damage the child's adjustment, and disciplines that are punitive can lead to anti-social attitudes. According to the results of research, that excessive protection can cause a variety of attitudes and feelings that will inhibit good adjustment.

Coopermith (1967) says that children who are raised under rigid or extreme family rules are more likely to have difficulty adjusting and facing greater difficulties in getting along in their environment. The opinion above is supported by Hurlock (1990) who said that excessive permissiveness will cause poor social adjustment behavior outside the home and will support high emotionality, while permissive attitudes that are not excessive will encourage good social adjustment and lead to creativity and attitudes mature in children.

As for the formation of a democratic child, animosity or hatred and displeasure among family members is revealed openly. As stated by Bachman (1967) that the more democratic a household will be, the more freely each member of the family will express things that he does not like. Besides that adolescents whose parents use democratic control, have a more harmonious relationship between parents and children and will affect their adjustment.

V. Conclusion

There is a relationship between family relations and adjustment in social life in the ethnic community, both in native Punjab adolescents and mixed Punjab adolescents. Aspects of family relations that show a greater relationship to adaptation in social life in the tribal community are permissive attitudes of parents and which relate to punishment of native Punjab adolescent men and women and democratic attitudes towards parents of mixed ethnic Punjab teenagers, boy and girl.

Families with all aspects of their complex problems are not only perceptions, but in totality all aspects of family psycho-social that affect adaptation need to be examined both in society specifically and in general. Adjustment to certain communities can not only be seen due to social factors, but it needs to be investigated. Other factors are thought to have a relationship and can affect one's adaptation, both to the community specifically and in general.

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